

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetic resources

Pigmentation and awning patterns of summer rice cultivars in Assam

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A wide range of variability occurs in characters of traditional summer (ahu) rice varieties. Classification on the basis of pigment distribution is useful documentation for identifying the germplasm. We mapped pigmentation patterns of four floral parts—sterile lemmas, lemma and palea, apiculus, and stigma—and the awning patterns of 797 cultivars.

Table 1. Distribution of pigment in 4 floral parts of summer traditional varieties of Assam, India.

Color	Floral parts (no.)			
	Lemma and palea	Sterile lemma	Apiculus	Stigma
No pigmentation (straw)	507	780	685	559
Brown	34	—	—	—
Deep brown	9	—	—	—
Brown spots on straw	8	—	—	—
Brown furrows on straw	6	—	—	—
Purple	11	17	71	238
Light purple	5	—	34	—
Black	217	—	7	—
Total	797	797	797	797

Nonpigmented organs were more frequent. Some variation in coloration was observed, and it was highest in the lemma and palea (flowering glumes), followed by the apiculus (Table 1). Awning patterns are presented in Table 2. □

Table 2. Awning patterns of the summer traditional varieties of Assam, India.

Type	Frequency (no.)
Awn absent	515
Short, partly awned	108
Short, fully awned	30
Long, partly awned	113
Long, fully awned	11
Total	797

Genetics

Studies on blast (BI) resistance genes in indica rice

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Work on the genetics of resistance to rice BI disease caused by *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. has identified 13 resistance genes. In general, a single dominant or two duplicate dominant genes govern resistance; in some cases, recessive genes and interactions of genes and gene linkage are found.

We studied the resistance genes for Chinese BI fungus races ZC3 and ZG1

in 10 indica rice cultivars. F₁, F₂, and B₁F₁ plants from crosses of susceptible (S)/resistant (R) cultivars and R/R cultivars were inoculated with the BI races.

The results indicate that in these cultivars, a single dominant or two duplicate dominant genes govern resistance (see table). Eleven dominant genes (*P-1* to *P-11*) were found. When the same plants were inoculated with both races, some genes did not segregate independently. Parental types were more frequent than recombinant types. This result indicates that some resistance genes are linked (e.g., *P-1* and *P-6* in Tetep).

The results also show that expression of resistance might be affected by some modifier genes or that there might be multiple alleles confirming

different levels of resistance at the same locus. If more races were used, more resistance genes would be identified. Inheritance analysis of rice BI resistance could be done easily and effectively, using only a few common fungus races. □

Genetic studies of the F₂ and F₃ of tall × semidwarf rice varieties

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We evaluated several genetic variables in F₂ and F₃ of three crosses involving

Genes for resistance to 2 rice BI races in 10 cultivars. Hangzhou, China.

Race	Resistance gene in each cultivar									
	Tetep	Chai-tang	Ai-mei-zao 3	IR36	IR58	Suweon 300	Hong-yang-ai 4	Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi	IR9782	Guo-ji-you-zha
ZC3	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1, P-2</i>	<i>P-1</i>	<i>P-1, P-2</i>	<i>P-3</i>	<i>P-4, P-5</i>
ZG1	<i>P-6</i>	<i>P-6</i>	<i>P-6</i>	<i>P-8</i>	<i>P-9</i>	<i>P-6, P-7</i>	<i>P-6, P-7</i>	<i>P-7</i>	<i>P-8</i>	<i>P-14, P-11</i>